

Health care manager's views on and approaches to implementing models for care processes

Jörgen ANDREASSON, Andrea ERIKSSON, Lotta DELLVE

*Health Sciences, University of Borås, Sweden and School of Health and Technology,
KTH-Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden*

1. Introduction

Previous research about organizational development in health care indicates that the kind of implementation can affect the outcome, and that the leadership is of a great importance for how the implementation is conducted. This article aims to focus managers' views on and approaches in organizational developments of care processes and their strategies to increase employees' engagement in development of care processes.

2. Methods

In-depth interviews with first and second line managers (n=30) in four Swedish hospitals were analyzed in line with constructivist Grounded Theory.

3. Results

The results describes managers positive view and expressed necessity to work with development of care processes, and their shared experience of challenges related to organization structures and demands. Experiences of success in implementing methods for care processes include to manage, to motivate and get the employees engaged in this work. "Mindful coaching of participation" emerged as central for managers to elicit this participation and handle top down initialized process development. The vertical approach was to sustaining integrity in adaptation and translation. The horizontal approaches were stepwise and negotiating and building participation, including to introducing silently, pushing and pulling to create interest, encouraging trial and error and empowering for solving the developments by sharing or dumping. The managers' were translating and repackaging the model of process development to create interest and to be received with acceptance by the employees.

4. Conclusions

Implementation of care processes needs a supportive and coaching leadership built on close manager-employee interaction, a mindfull implementation regarding pace at clinical levels as well as dedicated managers with competence to share responsibilities with teams and engaged employees with competence to share responsibilities over care processes. This also requires organizational supports in terms of provide time to work with development as well as support through organizational structures that assist work in process oriented way.